

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN NIGERIA AND THE SOVIET UNION: A REVIEW ON THE LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

This paper takes a comparison of the administrative system of Nigeria and that of the defunct Soviet Union. Using the Fred Riggs' Prismatic — Sala model of ecological analysis as its theoretical based, the paper contends that the socio-political and economic environment of societies shape and determine the principles and practice of administration in such societies. Data for this paper were sourced and analyzed using qualitative content analysis. The paper explores the ecology of the societies under study and their administrative systems. It inquires into whether or not their administrative systems conform to the Weberian ideal bureaucracy. It extrapolates their similarities and differences, challenges, prospects as well as lessons from the societies under study. The analysis reveals severe lacunas in the bureaucratic structure of both societies emanating from the ecological forces which surround the practice of administration in the societies under study. It was thus, recommended that, both societies pursue a revamping of their socio-political and economic structures as well as institutions so as to achieve a more diffracted and impersonal administrative system which enthrones merit, specialization and impersonality as against the prevailing infamous norm of a politicized public service and its attendant corruption and ineptitude which pervades the administrative systems of both societies.

KEYWORDS: *Administration, Bureaucracy, Ecology, Nigeria, Soviet Union*

INTRODUCTION

Cross national and cross cultural study of administrative systems are mostly conducted to enable countries learn from the experiences of other countries in similar or varying cultural settings. Thus, the Comparative Administrative Group (CAG) since its establishment has promoted research into administrative systems across different nations of the world (Sharma, Sadana & Kaur, 2012). Despite these efforts, scholarly research and publications seem lopsided as literature comparing the public administrative system of the Soviet Union to that of other countries are still scanty.

More so, researchers gave more attention on Western societies, especially on those of the United States, France, Britain and those of the newly emerging states of the third world — Africa, Asia and Latin America (Sharma, Sadana & Kaur, 2012). This paper attempts to fill

the literature gap by examining and analyzing the administrative system of the defunct Soviet Union in comparison to that of Nigeria. The Soviet Union is a defunct centrally planned socialist confederation. Its close apparition in the contemporary world is the Russian Federation. Though the Russia Federation is not synonymous with the Soviet Union, its administrative system provides a window through which the administrative system of the defunct Soviet Union can be understood. Nigeria on the other hand is an African liberal democratic state which practices a mixed economic system.

This paper attempts to compare these societies using the ecology approach as a logical framework of analysis. The Prismatic — Sala model of the ecology approach as advanced by Fred Riggs (1961) was the tool by which the administrative system of both societies under study were analyzed. The Spanish word 'Sala' (literarily translated to mean administration or government) was used by Riggs in reference to the administrative system of Prismatic Societies. According to Riggs, a prismatic society is one which has achieved certain level of differentiation, specialization of roles that is necessary for dealing with modern technology but is has failed to integrate these roles (Riggs quoted in Prasad, Prasad & Satyanarayana, 1997). The Prismatic — Sala model merges administrative tasks with traditional functions and its operations can only be understood in terms of the social and economic functions that it performs (Obiora, 2008). It attempts to explain the administrative system of transitional democracies in terms of ecology (political, social and economic environment of the societies under study).

Its use here is predicated on the fact that, administrative roles in the two societies under study are not clearly differentiated. Thus, an exploration of the unique socio-political and economic systems of these societies under study as well as their administrative systems is initiated with the intent of noting the observable nexus between them as well as their similarities and differences. More so, administrative roles in both societies under study are not clearly differentiated. Following the logic of this framework for analysis, this paper argues that the environment of both states shape and determine their administrative systems, hence, where similarities in the environments exist, same will be observed in the administrative system. Similarly, where differences exist in the environmental factors, the administrative system will also differ.

Data for this paper were derived from secondary source, specifically journal articles and texts that are related to the subject matter — the administrative system of the two societies under study. Thus, the data gathered were analyzed using qualitative content analysis as the technique for data analysis. Qualitative content analysis is a data analysis technique used to make replicable and valid inferences by interpreting and coding textual materials (Lyhne, Thisted & Bjerrum, 2025). For the purpose of specificity, this paper focuses on the bureaucracy in the societies under study. The paper is organized into seven parts consisting of the introduction, the ecology of the societies being compared, government and power sharing in the societies being compared, Public Administration (Bureaucracy) in the societies being compared, similarities and differences in the public administrative systems, the challenges, prospects and lessons for the public administrative systems of both societies and zthe conclusion. The next section thus addresses the issue of ecology.

Ecology — the Environment of Russia and Nigeria

The Soviet Union was midwife after the Bolshevik revolution of October 24th 1917 which remodeled the Russian economic, political and social system along socialist lines. The Union came into being through the amalgamation of six independent countries such as;

Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Armenia, Azerbaijan and Georgia, these nations agreed and signed the treaty of the Union in 1922 and later expanded to include 15 countries in its final years (Britannica, 2026). The union was essentially a confederacy as countries despite ceding their sovereignty to the center retained the sovereign status of their borders, flags and constitution as well as the right to secede (Eze, 2008). Adherence to the Union does not limit the autonomy of the Republics in the field of internal administration (Marxist.org). It is an association of Soviet Republics, based on the principle of voluntary centralism. The Federal Government, representing the peoples within the Union, exercises complete authority in all matters relating to the central administration of the Union, viz; armed defense, foreign relations, transport and communications, political security. The center also exercises supervisory role to secure coordination and uniformity in regulations affecting economic matters, labor and the general wellbeing.

The union was structured along socialist lines, this gave the state the total control of the means of production, distribution and exchange of goods and services. Decision making on who gets what, when and how was the sole responsibility of the central government. Governance was repressive and totalitarian and the economy was centrally controlled. This is aptly captured in the assertion of Eze (2008:282) where he summarized the Soviet Union under Stalin Thus;

... in 1927, Joseph V. Stalin assumed leadership of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union which translated to him also taking up office as the President of the

Union. Stalin's regime was repressive and totalitarian and he is best remembered for the policy of "command economy". He locked the national economy into a rigid system of state control. He utilized 5 —year economic plans which prescribed the periodic performance of every economic sector with heavy emphasis on heavy industry. Stalin successfully transformed the Soviet Union from a predominantly agrarian country into a world industrial power just before World War II. The Soviet Union also successfully battled the German forces in World War II and emerged alongside the United States as the two giant super powers in the world.

The two superpowers soon got locked in economic and ideological rivalry in what was later called the cold war. The Soviet Union proceeded to develop nuclear bomb and extended its influence to Eastern Europe in furtherance of its policy of propagating the sphere of socialist ideology in the world. The structure of the Soviet Union remained much the same under subsequent leaders such as Nikita Khrushchev (1953-64), Leonoid I. Brezhnev (1964 — 82), until the arrival of the last soviet leader Mikhail S. Gorbachev (1985 — 1991).

The quote above clearly captures the political, social and economic system of the Soviet Union. It shows that the system was under rigid economic and political control, it grew into a major world power from its hitherto agrarian state. Its attempts to spread the socialist ideology across other countries of Eastern Europe and consequent involvement in ideological rivalry with the capitalist countries of Western Europe spurred it to carry out space research and expeditions, develop nuclear bombs and other technological tools. The union eventually collapsed under Gorbachev (1985 -91) whom Eze (2008) described that he opened up the society to liberal influences.

Nigeria is a multicultural nation that was hitherto under the British Colonial Administrative control with over 250 ethnic and linguistic groupings. The area called Nigeria was forcefully annexed by the British around the late part of the 19th century and that of the early 20th

century (Ugwuka, 2025). The period of British occupation of Nigeria was marked by massive struggle for emancipation by nationalists from various parts of the country. The struggle gave rise to the emergence of political parties and groups which sought to liberate the country from the stronghold of colonialism. Due to the attainment of independence on the 1st of October, 1960, the country's political system gradually got engulfed in crises, this was occasioned by the preponderance of primordial and ethnic based consideration. The direct fallout of this mode of politicking in the country was the incursion of the military into the country's administration. To strengthen unity of the country, the military introduced such policies as the creation of states, the NY SC scheme, unity schools, etc. However, there remain deep rooted cleavages and divisions across all parts of the Nigerian State. This is aptly captured by Mustapha (1986) who identified eight (8) different levels of cleavages in the country. In his words;

The most important of which are: the cleavages between the three majority groups on the one hand and the 247-odd minority ethnic groups on the other; between the north and southern (1953 census); between the 36 states of the federation and the 6 zones three in the north and three in the south — into which they are grouped; and finally, between different religious affiliations. Some of these cleavages overlap; for example, the southeast zone overlaps with Igbo ethnicity and Christian religious affiliation while the northwest zone coincides with Hausa Fulani ethnicity and the Islamic faith.

Nigeria is a federal state which practice democratic system of government. The country operates an export based economy which is characterized by high rate of poverty, unemployment, mono-cultural dependence on crude oil, etc. (Ezeocha, 2020). Nigeria, often described as the most populous black nation in the world, home to over 200 million people and the seventh largest in the world. (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

Government and Power Sharing Structure in Nigeria and the Soviet Union

The Soviet Union started as a union of six states. Power Sharing and government structures in the Soviet Union consisted of the Congress of Soviets, the Central Executive Committee, and the council of people's Commissars containing such Commissariats as are relative to the work of a constituent Republic.

In the Soviet Union, the basis of the representative system rests upon the Soviets or elective councils. The Soviets, which are councils of delegates of a working citizenship, are designed to represent directly the productive life of the country. In the cities the basis of representation is mainly occupational, with the exception that persons in unorganized occupations (such as housewives) vote in geographic units. In the rural districts, where the productive life is homogeneous, the basis of representation is geographical. Each village elects its local Soviet. The various village Soviets send delegates to a township (Volost) Soviet, which elects an executive committee to exercise administrative powers in its jurisdiction. Similarly in the towns or cities delegates from the various productive groups of the community assemble in the town or city Soviet.

The District Congress of Soviets was composed of delegates from the village Soviets and from the Soviets of urban settlements of above 10,000 inhabitants. The delegates from the village Soviets were on the basis of one to 1,000 inhabitants, and in sparsely settled sections two or more villages may combine to send a delegate. The urban Soviets send one delegate to 200 electors. The Provincial Congress of Soviets is composed of delegates from Urban Soviets, from Soviets of industrial settlements with a population of 5,000, and from the

Volost Soviets. In this fashion, from the original local or occupational unit, the Soviets pyramid up to the Congresses of Soviets representing the larger administrative divisions, the autonomous republics and areas, the constituent republics, and the entire Soviet Union. The supreme organ of authority is the All - Union Congress of Soviets. This is composed of representatives of town and township Soviets, and of provincial Congresses of Soviets. It meets at least once in two years. During the interval between the All- Union Congresses of Soviets, the supreme authority devolves upon the Central Executive Committee, consisting of the Council of the Union and the Council of Nationalities. The Council of the Union is elected by the Congress from representatives of the six constituent republics, in proportion to their population. It had in all, 450 members. The Council of Nationalities is formed of representatives of the Constituent and Autonomous Republics, five delegates from each, and of representatives of autonomous areas, one delegate from each, in all 139 members. The members of the Council are elected at the Republican and regional congresses of Soviets.

The Central Executive Committee meets three times a year. During the interval between sessions of the Central Executive Committee, the Presidium of the Committee is the supreme legislative, executive, and administrative organ of authority. The Presidium of the Central Executive Committee consisted of 27 members, nine representing the Council of the Union, nine representing the Council of Nationalities and nine elected by the two Councils in joint session. The Council of People's Commissars is the executive and directive organ of the Central Executive Committee. Members of the Council are elected for two years. The same general scheme is also repeated in each of the Autonomous Republics, and likewise in the Autonomous Areas except that the latter have no Council of Commissars. In their scheme the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee fulfills the functions of the Council of People's Commissars. In the Soviet administrative scheme, the People's Commissariats are divided into three categories:

Commissariats of the whole Union alone; Commissariats which form part of the administrative scheme of the Constituent Republics, as well as of the Federal Government; Commissariats which appear in the Constituent Republics alone. Commissariats of the whole Union alone are: Foreign Affairs, Army and Navy, Transport, Posts and Telegraphs, Trade and Commerce. The divisions of Trade and Commerce dealing with the internal trade are also in the Constituent Republics. Commissariats in both the Federal Government and the Governments of the Constituent Republics are: Supreme Economic Council, Labor, Finance, Workers' and Peasants' Inspection. Commissariats of the Constituent Republics only: Agriculture, Internal Affairs, Justice, Education, Health, Social Welfare.

A pyramidal representative form, similar to that adopted for the entire Union, with local and town Soviets as the base, obtains in each of the Constituent Republics and in the autonomous republics and areas. The permanent judicial system was established on January 1, 1923. It includes People's (District) Courts of both civil and criminal jurisdiction, Provincial Courts of Second Instance, Supreme Courts of the Constituent Republics, and the Supreme Court of the Union, subdivided into various courts of special jurisdiction. There are also special Labor Courts, which may be the local People's Court sitting in special session for labor cases.

In Nigeria, The 1999 constitution provides for a bicameral legislature which consist of 360 - member House of Representatives (the Green Chamber) and 109-member Senate (the Red Chamber). The president heads the executive branch. The judiciary includes a Supreme Court and lower courts. Executive power is vested in the president, who is simultaneously Head of state and head of government and moreso, as Commander in chief of the Armed

forces. The president is eligible for two four-year terms. The Federal Executive Council, or cabinet, includes; the President and at least two representatives from each of the 36 states and one from the federal capital territory.

The National Assembly is bicameral in nature, consisting of a 109-member Senate and a 360-member House of Representatives, constitutes the country's legislative branch. Three senators represent each of Nigeria's 36 states, and one additional senator represents the capital city of Abuja. Seats in the House of Representatives are allocated based on the population of the various states. Therefore, the number of House members from each state differs. Members of the National Assembly are elected for an unlimited tenure based on their performance as measure satisfactory by their constituents.

The judicial branch comprise the Supreme Court, the Court of Appeal, the Federal High Court, and at the state high courts, sharia courts, and customary courts. The president appoints members of the Supreme Court through the recommendation of the National Judicial Commission and subject to confirmation by the Senate. Competition between branches of government and between levels of government also remains weak. The executive has dominating power over the other branches of government which undermine the financial autonomy of the other branches (Nebeife, 2026).

The executive often determines the leadership of the National Assembly, as do the state governors in regards to the state legislatures. Neither the civil service nor the judiciary is typically powerful or impartial enough to act as an effective constraint on the power of the executive, although the federal judiciary has shown itself to be an increasingly important check. Likewise, the relations between federal, state, and local governments are also top-down, both in terms of revenues and the authoritative use of force. States do not have their own independent tax bases or independent police.

Nigeria is divided administratively into the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja) and 36 states, which are organized into the following six zones: South—West Zone—Lagos, Ekiti, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, and Oyo; South—South Zone—Akwa, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Ibom, and Rivers; South— East Zone—Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo; North—West Zone—Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Jigawa, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara; North—Central Zone—Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nassarawa, Niger, and Plateau: and North—East Zone—Adamawa, Bauchi, Bornue, Gomber, Taraba, and Yobe.

Each of Nigeria's 36 states has an elected governor and a House of Assembly. The governor is elected for a maximum of two four-year terms. The number of members to the House of Assembly of a state is based on population (three to four times the number of delegates each state sends to the federal House of Representatives) and therefore varies from state to state within the range of 24 to 40. Nigeria's states are subdivided into 774 local government areas, each of which is governed by a council Chairman that is responsible for administering basic needs of the local people.

Nigeria's legal system is based on a combination of statutory (legislative) law, English common law, customary law, and, in the north, Islamic law (sharia). Nigeria's federal and state courts apply statutory and English common law, whereas local courts recognize the legitimacy of customary and Islamic law. Universal suffrage at age 18 applies to all elections. Winning candidates are determined according to the British first-past- the-post system, whereby a plurality of the votes ensures victory. Also under this system, members of the National Assembly represent distinct geographic constituencies.

Bureaucracy in the Soviet Union — An Overview

Principles and practices of administration in the defunct Soviet Union was a radical departure from the present ideals of administrative practice. It was at variance with the Weberian ideal bureaucratic model as is understood in the developed world (Goetz 2001 cited in Eze 2008). The soviet system could not accommodate the Weberian idea that there should be a separation of political and administrative spheres and that the administrative machinery in a public bureaucracy should be relatively autonomous. The rationale for this can be conveniently attributed to the centrally planned ecology of the Soviet world.

The centrally planned nature of the Soviet Union made it relatively cumbersome to adopt the ideal bureaucratic tenets of Max Weber which according to Prasad, Prasad and Satyarayana (1997, Wicaksono & Aji, 2025) emphasizes hierarchy, legality, technical competence, impersonality and merit based career system. In the Weber's ideal bureaucracy staffers who are appointed function according to the following criteria; members are personally free, observing only the impersonal duties of the offices, there is clear hierarchy of offices, the function of each office one occupies are clearly spelt out, officials are appointed on the basis of a contract, selection/recruitment is based on professional qualification, there is career structure and promotion is based on merit, officials may possess neither the post nor the resources which go with it, there is a unified control and discipline system (Wicaksono & Aji,2025). The major position of Weberism can be summarized as 'rational merit based employment and promotion for effective and efficient impersonal administration. This is why the idea of bureaucracy is often interpreted to mean an organization consisting of hierarchically placed officials with rules and regulations guiding the conduct of their affairs.

In contrast to the above criteria and requirements for the ideal Weberian bureaucracy, the soviet administration was devoid of insulation of administration from politics. There was an absence of what Woodrow Wilson would call the politics administration dichotomy. The soviet administration was intertwined and penetrated by the ruling party, the Communist Party of the Soviet Union at almost all levels (Eze, 2008). Using the party administered Nomenklatura system, recruitment was politicized in principle and was in practice much more personalized. The Nomenklatura system is a system in communist party states whereby the party maintained domination of significant positions in both government and society by vetting appointments to all major posts in society, drawing them from a list of suitable candidates (Eze, 2008).

Also, in the Soviet Union, rules were not strictly adhered to. This made Thompson (2005) aver quite strongly that "in the Soviet period, rule violation were often tacitly condoned in the interest of task accomplishment". Similarly, Eze (2008) posits that, .if rules came into conflict with the need to fulfill a task plan, the later tended to take precedence". This clearly contradicts the Weberian idea of bureaucracy which places primacy on strict adherence to rules. In addition, the Soviet administrative system had no clear functional division of labour but was characterized by complex and often overlapping jurisdiction and lines of authority. According to Eze (2008), the political leadership created the confusion in order to use it to facilitate monitoring and control of officials.

Summarily, the Soviet administrative system was highly personalized, patron-client relationships dictated who gets what, when and how in the civil service rather than the enforcement of rules and formalized codes of behavior. Despite its complex and apparent well defined formal institutions, the Soviet administrative machinery relied heavily on an informal structure of personal networks within the party-state apparatus to function. It was a

system where realms of authority was more or less vested on individuals rather than offices, The end result of such personalized administrative structures were the weakening of the state institutional capacity and encouragement of rent-seeking and corruption amongst the rank and file of civil service (Eze, 2008). High level officials exploited this practice to their personal advantage by appointing only trusted personal associates to key positions in public establishments.

Bureaucracy in Nigeria — An Overview

Public Administration in Nigeria owes its root and growth to its history as a colony of Great Britain. Generally, the Nigerian Public Administrative system is structured in line with that of the British (Akinola 2017). In its formative stage, it was intended to serve as the instrument of colonial accomplishment in areas of maintenance of law and order and revenue generation. With time, the development of the Nigerian state triggered the modification of the nature, functions and scope of administration in the country via reforms which aimed at improving the prospects of the country's administrative system and increasing the involvement of Nigerians in the Nigerian public administrative system.

Several reforms has been initiated in the past in Nigeria in order to improve on the Administrative system, these among others are; Hint Committee (1934), Bridge Committee (1942), Miller Commission (1946), Foot Commission (1948), Adebo Commission (1953), Gorsuch Commission (1954) and a host of other pre independence public service reform commissions. Also, during the post — independence era, a number of commissions were set up to reform the Nigerian Public Service, they include such commissions as; the Elwood Commission (1966), Morgan commission (1963), Adebo Commission (1971), Udoji Public Service Commission Review (1972 — 1974), Phillips Panel (1985), etc. These reforms all contributed to bringing about a relatively developed public administrative system in Nigeria as such administrative activities as recruitment, remuneration, promotion, etc. were conducted based on established rules (Omisore. & Okofu, 2014). Similarly, most of the tenets of Weber's bureaucracy were promoted on paper as ideals of merit (based on either qualification or seniority), impersonality, impartiality, etc. were all encoded in the document containing the public service rules (General Order).

However, despite these lofty ideals existing on paper, the Nigerian Public service still fall below the standards set by Weber as his criterion an ideal bureaucracy. The Nigerian public service over the years had been politicized to the extent that most top officials openly supported the government of the day (Akinola 2017). The introduction of the quota system of recruitment and promotion adherence to the federal-character principle, and the constant interference of the government in the day to day operation of the civil service, especially through frequent changes in top officials and massive purges, meant that political factors rather than merit alone played a major role in the public service (Mutillah, 2014). Eme and Ugwu, (2011) noted that the enthronement of federal character principle of recruitment and other spoils system techniques have sacrificed efficiency and effectiveness in the Nigerian civil service. This was captured more emphatically by Omotosho (2001) where he pointed out that "merit is often jettisoned on the altar of ethnicity and religion in recruitment into the public service in Nigeria". Subsequent observation by Salisu, (2001) posits that considerable political interference in the process of personnel administration had led to improper delegation of power, ineffective supervision and corruption in the Nigerian civil service in recent time. Hence according to him, result in official apathy that has so far culminated into

unauthorized and unreasonable absenteeism, lateness and idleness and particularly poor workmanship in the Nigerian civil service.

The prebendal mode of entry into the public service in Nigeria often shape the quality of service delivery amongst public servants. Rules are often violated at will and public positions are often used to accrue personal gratifications. This is clear in the work of Akinola (2017) where he pointed out that;

Nigerian public service is plagued with myriads of problems that have made it difficult for the system to function effectively and efficiently... most public servants engage in sharp practices, most of them keep business letter headed papers, invoices, receipts and other companies owned by them and this affects their contribution to development.

The position presented above presents a clear picture of the nature of Nigerian Public Administration. It shows that though rules exist on paper to ensure conformity with the Weber's ideals of a bureaucracy, like the Soviet Union, there are ecological factors mitigating against the attainment of the standard. Socio-cultural, political and economic factors tend to prompt a deviation from the norm even when they are entrenched in a legal document. The Next section, explores the similarities and differences between the Public Administrative systems of the two societies under study.

Similarities between Public Administration in the Soviet Union and Nigeria

From the discourse on the Public Administration of the two societies presented above, certain basic similarities have been noticed to exist in the administrative system of both societies. The Soviet Union was a socialist state while Nigeria operates a mixed economy, exhibiting both socialist and liberal traits. These similarities emanates from similar ecological factors found in the societies. The major point of similarity to note is the fact that, public administration in both societies do not conform to Weber's notion of ideal bureaucracy The specific similarities in the practices of public administration in the societies under study are presented below:

Frist, it is noticeable that recruitment in the two societies are not strictly based on merit. The Soviet Union incorporates its public servants through the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (CPSU)'s Nomenkletura system which allows the party to maintain dominance of significance positions by selecting from names of suitable candidates. In same vein, under the Nigerian experience, entry into the public service is highly politicized. Public offices and positions are often viewed as prebends used by those in power for the benefit of themselves, their families and their close allies.

It is in this line of thought that Richard Joseph described politics in Nigeria as politics of prebendalism. Also, such considerations like federal character, quota system, catchment area, etc. which have found its way into the lexicon of the Nigerian administrative system defy the criterion of merit. Similarly, consequent upon the highly politicized Administrative system in both societies, there emanates highly personalized bureaucracies. As have been pointed out in the preceding section, public officials in both societies engage in sharp practices which blurs the dividing line between the official and the personal. Administration has come to be largely personalized in Nigeria (Akinola, 2017) and in Russia (Eze, 2008).

Differences between Public Administration in the Soviet Union and Nigeria

Though numerous points of similarities can be identified in the administrative systems of the societies under study, it is noticeable that the ecology of the societies are not entirely the same. The defunct Soviet Union was a centrally planned communist non-African state while Nigeria is a liberal democratic African state. The Soviet Union was based on socialist values and ideologies, the Nigerian state is based on liberal/capitalist values and ideologies. Since administration is shaped by the constellation of value systems political, economic, social and technological forces which characterize the environment, it is truism that these differences in the environment will translate to differences in the administrative systems.

The first noteworthy point of difference is that, in Nigeria, there is the Federal and State civil service commission which is in charge of personnel administration in the country. Also, there are rules establishing merit (based on qualification and seniority) as a criteria for recruitment and promotion in the public service. The Public Service Rules (General Order) in Nigeria specifies the modalities for ensuring merit based recruitment, promotion and placement of staffs in the Nigerian public service, such was absent in the defunct Soviet Union. The CPSU had the sole preserve to control all aspects of the country's administrative system in line with its Nomenkletura system (Eze, 2008).

Also, the primacy placed on the adherence to rules and bureaucratic processes differ in the two societies. In the Soviet Union, violation of rules was often tacitly condoned in the interest of task accomplishment (Eze, 2008), however, Nigerian Bureaucrats and public administrators often insist on strict adherence to rules even if there will arise some anticipated consequences such as reduction in efficiency (Olayemi & Muhammed, 2016).

Challenges, Prospects and Lessons for the two Societies

The administrative systems of the two societies compared are faced with similar challenges. While Eze (2008) pointed out that, corruption pervaded the Russian public administration, other scholars like (Okotoni, 2003; Ogunrotifa, 2012), also commented on the rising corruption in the Nigerian State. Corruption is a major problem limiting public bureaucracies in Nigeria and Russia. Corrupt practices occur in nearly all ministries, departments and agencies where virtually all members of the bureaucracy are involved (Okotoni, 2003). Graft and corruption include bribery, extortion and nepotism are characterized by the subordination of public interests to private aims and violations of the norms of duty and welfare, accompanied by secrecy, betrayal, deception and a callous disregard for any consequences suffered by the public. The public consider graft and corruption to be widespread and persistent in Nigerian civil service (Ogunrotifa, 2012). Actually, corruption has become more or less a permanent problem in Nigerian civil service.

Bureaucratic corruption in Nigeria continues to grow in leaps and bounds. Therefore, many civil servants have defrauded and embezzled government money earmarked for developmental purposes. Most of them would demand for money before rendering their statutory duties to the members of the public. This made development difficult through civil service (Omotosho, 2001). Currently, the Nigerian civil service is fraught with the following problems and discontents, such as lack of measurable objectives, inadequate evaluations, mismanagement of time, inadequate facilities, disorganization, personnel management and over centralization.

Conclusion

Thus far, this paper has compared public administration in Nigeria and the Soviet Union. It has noted that the Soviet Union is a defunct centrally planned state which was based on socialist ideology. Its administrative structure was patterned in accordance with the idea of democratic centrality. The dominant party was deeply engrossed in the administration of the country. On the other hand, Nigeria is a liberal democratic state which operates a mixed economy. Its administrative structure is patterned in consonance with that of their former colonial masters, the British. Its public service is however, highly personalized. This is as Wu cited in Ezeani (2006) has succinctly noted that "when and if public officials are allowed to run for public offices even on the condition of resignation, they are bound to exhibit partisan tendencies in the execution of policies".

It has thus, been established that the ecology — environment of both societies shape their administrative system. Administration is culture bound. Hence, the centrally planned nature of the Soviet state created a state (instead of public) service wherein, administrative functions are carried out at personal levels, rules are sacrificed on the altar of task accomplishment and policies are implemented to promote the achievement of the aspirations of the dominant party and by extension, the soviet government. Similarly, the underdeveloped nature of the Nigerian state and its constitution which allows public officials to participate in politics has created a system wherein, the execution of administrative functions are personalized and, there is an emphasis on strict adherence to rules even at the detriment of task accomplishment.

It is thus concluded that, in the two societies compared, ecological factors have shaped the administrative system, hence, administrative systems are similar where similarities exist in the ecology and they differ where differences exist. This is evident in the fact that, while the defunct Soviet Union was a union of socialist states, Nigeria operates a mixed economy, with both liberal and socialist attributes, hence, the administrative system of both societies exhibits traits of the spoils system. On the other hand, while the personnel administration in the Soviet administrative system was organized based on the Nomenkletura system, in Nigeria, there is the federal and state civil service commissions which are in charge of personnel administration.

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